

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D3.5 – Secondary data capture and interoperability I

WP3 Personalized Holistic Health Records

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Executive summary

The purpose of this iHelp deliverable, D3.5 “Secondary data capture and interoperability I”, a public report, is to act as an inventory of secondary data for the iHelp clinical studies, ensuring that all clinical partners know what has been made available for extracting information from their end-users, mostly patients, but in cases of preventive studies, also the general public. No matter their status (patient, or *citizen*), end-users in iHelp are study participants, and this is how they are referred to in this document. The deliverable also documents the choices made on what to measure and what to simply ask the study participants to provide, trying to strike a balance between loading people with devices (and cost) but also asking too much of them in terms of data entry. In that respect it is of interest outside the iHelp community, serving as a data collection manual outside of the strict clinical setting.

This document is delivered in M10 (October 2021), between the two phases of requirement collection. It follows up on the early requirements reported in D2.1, “State of the art and requirements analysis I” in M6 and the discussions between the partners responsible for secondary data collection and the clinical partners. As a result, a mature secondary data inventory has been drafted. It is followed by D2.2, “State of the art and requirements analysis II” in M12, where the final requirements will be documented, possibly leading to some changes in the inventory. Any such changes will be documented in the second version of this deliverable, D3.6 “Secondary data capture and interoperability II”, due in M22 (October 2022).

1 Introduction

We define “Secondary data” as the data collected from the study participants in a non-clinical setting. Such data are collected, ingested into iHelp and complement the primary, clinical data in the HHR.

1.1 Deliverable purpose

The purpose of this iHelp deliverable, D3.5 “Secondary data capture and interoperability I”, a public report, is to act as a manual for secondary data collection, both within and beyond iHelp. Secondary data are introduced, discussing what can be collected, what is actually collected for the clinical studies of iHelp, and how this is facilitated, using both automated measurements and reports.

Actually, a successful secondary data collection system is the one that achieves a balance between usage of devices for measurements (which incur cost and demand the attention of the study participants) and the request for reports (which incur manual data entry from the study participants).

1.2 Target audience

The target audience for this deliverable consists of individuals both within and outside of the iHelp project. The following iHelp partners will be using this deliverable:

- Internal to the secondary data capture task, software engineers will use the information for implementing the necessary widgets the study participants will be reporting data with. Also, the questionnaires involved will be identified and implemented using the designated computer-readable representation. Finally, the secondary data inventory will be used by the partners mapping the data attributes to the HHR.
- The data scientists building the HHR, as well as the ML engineers building the iHelp models, will be informed on the secondary data inventory.
- The clinical partners will be informed of the options available for collecting information from their study participants, in order to guide them through the use of the data collection system at the recruitment phase.

As to the clinical study community beyond iHelp, this deliverable is documenting the project’s attempt for striking a balance between the measurement burden (hardware that needs participants’ attention and its cost) and the reporting burden (repeated requests for manual entry of data).

1.3 Deliverable context

The requirements from the clinical partners are the starting point for determining what to capture. Their early version is found in D2.1 “State of the art and requirements analysis I”, delivered in M6. These early requirements have been discussed in bilateral meetings between the clinical partners and those responsible for the secondary data extraction. As a result, these requirements have been matured, and are used as the “wish-list” in this deliverable and are to be documented in D2.2 “State of the art and requirements analysis II” due to be released in M12 of the project (December 2021).

The system collecting the secondary data is Healthentia, an e-clinical platform, developed by Innovation Sprint, the iHelp partner leading the secondary data collection efforts of iHelp. This is a mature product,

and hence only the new modules needed are to be specified by iHelp, both in this deliverable and more formally in D2.6 “Functional and Non-Functional Specifications I” also to be delivered in M10.

Healthentia is used as an edge processing platform in iHelp, playing the role of a composite sensor. The role of Healthentia as a source is described in D2.4 “Conceptual model and reference architecture I” delivered in M8 and the details on how this is achieved are presented here.

The primary and secondary data utilize the same ingestion pipeline in iHelp. Hence data ingestion in general, and not only primary data, is discussed in D3.3 “Primary data capture and ingestion I” also to be delivered in M10. Pointers to that document are only included here.

Secondary data mapping into the HHR is also part of the secondary data efforts of iHelp. Preliminary information on the HHR is to be found in D3.1 “Data Modelling and Integrated Health Records: Design and open specification I” delivered in M8. The mapping itself is only briefly discussed here. It is the central focus of the second version of this deliverable, D3.6 “Secondary data capture and interoperability II” to be delivered in M22. The information in that second version should affect the final HHR specification in D3.2 “Data Modelling and Integrated Health Records: Design and open specification II” to be delivered in M32.

1.4 Deliverable structure

The secondary data are defined in contrast to the primary in the beginning of Section 2. They are split into the four different categories characterising the life of people outside the clinical setting. A discussion then begins from D2.1, towards the analysis and presentation of today’s clinical partners’ wish-list.

The way to collect secondary data is discussed in Section 3. The discussion is originally generic, as befits a public deliverable, but then drills down to the particulars of the iHelp secondary data. The wish-list of Section 3 is broken down in attributes to be measured by devices and attributes to be reported by the study participants. The section concludes with the iHelp secondary data inventory of what and how to capture.

The secondary data collected following the means of Section 3 are raw, in the sense that they are directly collected from sensors or study participants. Section 4 is about processing the raw data into more meaningful quantities, like habits and trends.

Raw and processed secondary data need to be ingested into the iHelp platform and mapped into HHR. Section 5 follows this process, starting with a discussion about the Healthentia e-clinical platform and its place as a sensor in the overall iHelp architecture. Secondary data ingestion is then outlined, following the same pipeline as the primary data and a preliminary discussion of HHR mapping concludes the section.

Finally, the deliverable is concluded in Section 6.

2 Secondary data: What to collect

Data is the new medicine [1]. Data (when shared, reused in a privacy-respecting way and maintaining the control to the people providing it) can improve patient outcomes, foster research and accelerate deployment of novel health services [2]. In the health domain, and for the purpose of this deliverable, data comes in two flavours: inside and outside of the clinical setting.

2.1 Primary vs. secondary data

Health data are readily associated with clinical tests performed invasively on samples taken from our bodies, or non-invasively using modern depicting techniques. Such data, obtained in a clinical setting, is of paramount importance, is termed primary in the iHelp project, but certainly does not form the complete spectrum of health data.

Hippocrates (approx. 460-370 BC), the father of medicine believed that disease was not a punishment inflicted by the gods but rather the product of environmental factors, diet, and living habits, a fact that is well-established today. Our living habits can be enumerated using data attributes about our lifestyle, obtained in our natural environment, outside of the clinical setting. This data is termed Real-World Data (RWD) and in iHelp is distinguished from the clinical, primary data by being termed secondary data, more to indicate the different collection setting than to attempt to compare the importance of the two (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The two sources of iHelp data – primary (clinical) and secondary (real-world data).

RWD are formally defined by the FDA as “*data related to patient health status and/or the delivery of health care routinely collected from EHRs, claims and billing data, data from product and disease registries, patient-generated data including home-use settings, and data gathered from other sources that can inform on health status, such as mobile devices.*” [3].

While clinical data is generated sparingly, during testing or hospitalisation sessions, RWD is generated continuously, throughout the days, weeks and months of our lifetime. It would thus be good practice to actually collect RWD in a continuous mode, rather than the sporadic mode in which clinical data are collected. Section 3 discusses how this can happen, and the practices followed in iHelp.

RWD comprises attributes that enumerate different important aspects of the way we live our lives. The attributes are grouped in the physiological, psychological, social and environmental categories discussed next.

2.1.1 Physiological attributes

The physiological attributes of RWD have to do with the human body, its activities and adverse events. They are mostly measured using activity trackers and/or smartphones, but are also reported.

Activity related attributes are *steps walked, distance walked, elevation (or floors climbed)*, energy dissipation, time spent in different activity intensity zones (e.g., mild, moderate and high intensity physical activity, as it is formally defined as a function of age) and exercise activities (walking, running, cycling, etc.), as well as their distribution in the day. Presence indoors or outdoors can also be of importance. Specialized physical activity can also be measured via composite tests like the six-minute walk test (6MWT), the frailty test or games specifically designed to measure muscular responses (tapping on a mobile phone screen for Parkinson's disease or performing other exercises while monitored and analysed by depth cameras to measure features important in stroke or accident rehabilitation). All these tests are scripted and hence can be measured using sensors and audio-visual instructions to the people on their smartphone.

Attributes related to the functioning of the heart include the continuous measurements of the heart rate variability and the time spent in different heart rate zones, as well as the daily resting heart rate measurement.

Sleep related attributes include continuous measurements on the time spent in the different sleep stages (awake in bed, light, REM, deep sleep).

Other physiological attributes can be self-reported by the participant. Symptoms of interest in general or to specific therapeutic areas (e.g., headache, body temperature, blood pressure, pains, diarrhoea, fatigue, nausea), including their intensity can be collected. Weight should be regularly reported, and less so height (especially at younger or older ages). Nutrition is paramount, starting at a higher level with the consumption of food categories of interest, but more detailed analysis can also be used when available. Water, coffee, tea, refreshments and alcohol intake can be reported. Finally, the menstrual cycle can also be of importance.

2.1.2 Psychological attributes

The psychological RWD attributes refer to the emotions of the study participants. They are mostly reported and include at a high-level simple emotional state self-assessment, but when deemed necessary the collected information goes deeper using standardized reports from professional therapists monitoring the patients.

Measurements can also be used to indirectly capture psychological aspects. Emotion can be recognized from video recordings of the face, the voice audio or the social media text posts. Places visited (which, how diverse they are) are also an indication of the psychological state. Aspects like the weather or spending unusual time in commuting can have some importance.

2.1.3 Social attributes

The social RWD attributes enumerate study participants' social life. Such information can be measured indirectly using attributes about the usage of the phone (diversity, duration, frequency of calls) and social media (diversity, number, frequency of interactions).

More direct information can be reported using questionnaires on activities with friends, family or co-workers, or can be obtained in conversation with a digital virtual coach.

2.1.4 Environmental attributes

The environmental RWD attributes attempt to enumerate the environment the study participants live in. They include reported environmental indicators for the assessment of the quality of life, like the 11 attributes of the OECD better life index [4].

Precise measurements of living or working environment quality can be obtained by integrating relevant commercial devices (e.g., for air quality analysis), or by integrating with data services that report e.g., Air Quality Index at specific locations.

2.2 Discussing clinical requirements

The RWD attributes presented in Section 2.1 are generic, and should be specialized for every therapeutic domain. Nevertheless, they had been the starting point for the possibilities available to clinical partners in terms of secondary data collection. The initial processing resulted to the secondary data requirements in D2.1 “State of the art and requirements analysis I”, Section 4.3. Further analysis after the submission of D2.1 in M6 of the project has resulted to the consolidated requirements across all clinical partners shown in Table 1 (physiological) and Table 2 (psychological, social and quality of life).

Table 1: Physiological RWD consolidated requirements across the five clinical partners.

Category	Attributes/parameters	UOM	FPG	HDM	MUP	TMU
Physical activity	Steps	x	x	x		x
	Floors		x			x
	Energy burned	x	x			x
	Time in different activity zones		x			x
Exercise sessions	Start time	x	x			
	Duration	x	x			
	Type	x	x			
	Energy burned	x	x			
Heart	Resting heart rate	x	x	x		
	Max heart rate	x	x	x		
	Time in different heart rate zones	x				
Sleep	Start time	x	x	x	x	x
	Duration	x	x		x	x
	Time in different sleep stages	x	x		x	
	Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index [5]					x
Nutrition	Consumption of food categories (meat, veg, grain etc)	x	x	x	x	x
	Liquids	x	x		x	x
	Food Frequency Questionnaire [6]	x				
	Food diary with rations [7]	x				
Symptoms	Symptom assessment questionnaire [8]					x

The physical activity attributes and exercise sessions can be collected using an activity tracker, or a smartphone (as long as it is kept with the study participant most of the time). Physical activities cannot be entered manually, while exercise sessions (at least start time and duration) can.

The heart can only be monitored continuously with an activity tracker. Sporadic measurements can be added manually.

The sleep attributes can be collected by an activity tracker. Start and duration can be entered manually. The questionnaire is a self-assessment.

All nutrition, symptom, psychological and health/quality of life attributes are manually reported.

Table 2: Psychological, social and quality of life RWD consolidated requirements across the five clinical partners.

Category	Attributes/parameters	UOM	FPG	HDM	MUP	TMU
Psychological	Mood self-assessment via 5-level smileys	X	X	X	X	X
	The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scales [9]	X	X	X	X	
	Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale [10]	X	X	X	X	
	Body Awareness Questionnaire [11]	X	X	X		
	Subjective Happiness Scale [12]	X	X	X	X	
	Motivation, risk averse, big 5	X	X	X		
	Locus of Control Questionnaire [13]	X	X	X		
	Health Behaviour and Stages of Change Questionnaire [14]	X	X	X	X	
	Symptom assessment questionnaire [8]					X
Social	Types and frequent use of social platform		X	X	X	X
	Supportive messaging with moderation		X	X		
	Opportunities for forming new health habits	X	X	X	X	
	Use of mobile apps		X	X		X
Health/Quality of life	Overall health rating by participants [15]	X	X	X	X	X
	Health literacy (HLS-EU_Q16) [16]	X		X		
	Diseases: diabetes, hypertension, pancreatitis, cirrhosis, hepatitis	X				X
	Family history of pancreatic cancer	X		X		X
	Process of change [17]	X	X	X	X	
	Smoking					X
	Height & weight	X				X
	Quality of life (EQ-5D) [18]	X		X	X	
	Quality of life for patients (EORTC QLQ-C30) [19]		X	X		X
	Quality of life for pancreatic cancer patients (EORTC QLQ-PAN26) [20]		X	X		
	Activities of Daily Living: hygiene, continence mgmt., dressing, feeding, ambulating			X		
Frailty measure			X			

Regarding the social attributes, the supportive message is an opportunity to send a message from one study participant to all others, after being approved by a moderator. The collection of the message is a free text report. The moderation can happen at the portal app. The delivery of the approved message can be done by the virtual coach. The opportunities for forming new health habits is a questionnaire. The use of mobile apps and social platforms can be reported but also can in principle be measured. There are authorization implications though that make such measurements difficult to implement but also to enable by the study participants.

The RWD in Table 1 and Table 2 constitute the iHelp clinical partners' wish-list. In the following section this will be analysed in terms of feasibility to derive the secondary data inventory.

3 Secondary data: How to collect

RWD are collected outside the clinical setting, directly from the study participants using ubiquitous, easy to operate devices, or simply by asking people about the necessary information.

3.1 Measuring from devices

RWD measurements involve devices that are commonly used by people. An important source of physiological information is the activity tracker. These are consumer devices gaining popularity amongst health- and wellness- aware people. Study participants can already own one, easily get a cheap one, or the studies can distribute them for free as a participation incentive, especially for longer studies. Other devices can be scales and ubiquitous medical devices (e.g., thermometers, blood pressure monitors, SPO2 monitors). Even more specialised medical devices can be included here, of the type used at home not by the general population, but by certain patient categories.

No matter the devices, there are two modes of measurement collection: the automatic and the manual. Automatic measurement collection refers to having the measurement device integrated with the data collection system, the measurements flowing from the device into the RWD collection system in an unattended manner. Manual measurement collection refers to having the study participant reading out the measurement from the device and manually reporting the measurement to the RWD collection system.

The automatic is clearly the preferred option, the only one when the measurements have high volume and/or frequency. It minimises study participants' burden and data entry errors. It is of this option only that "measurement from devices" refers to. The methods to do so are outlined in Section 3.1.1, while devices involved in the iHelp measurements are discussed in Section 3.1.2. The manual measurement option is actually a case of study participant report, covered in Section 3.2.

3.1.1 Methods

Devices can be integrated with RWD capturing systems in two ways: employing the devices manufactures' provided API or SDK. To understand the difference, it is important to understand the flow of information from the device.

All devices have a short-range communication capability, which is almost always Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE). This necessitates the use of another device that collects the information, called a controller, base station, edge node or bridge depending on the manufacturer. In case of domotics devices being fixed in some location, this controller is a fixed device, located somewhere in the home. In case of wearables, the most natural choice is to use the mobile phone that is mostly around the study participant as a controller, in which case the controller is some software installed on the phone. The controller receives the information from the device(s) it is paired with using the BLE protocol of its communication module. It then transmits this information to the servers of the device manufacturers using WLAN. The study participants control the devices using SW on their mobile phones and/or on the web. They also view (and control) their data using the same apps. The process is depicted in the upper section of Figure 2, the 3rd-party device section.

Since the study participants need to be more in control of their data and the advent of GDPR, device manufactures typically offer means to the study participants to get their data, not just view it. Data exports in files have long been available, but recently there are more automated options, allowing the study

participants to get their data in online ways. APIs and/or SDKs are being offered so that requests are forwarded by third-party SW systems to get the data. The study participants only need to authorise these third-party SW systems to collect the data on their behalf. This is exactly the method used in iHelp, with the details being discussed in Section 5.1.

When a device manufacturer offers an API to get data, then the data is captured from the cloud platform of the integrated device. The API offers endpoints to be used by an authenticated entity to get data they are authorized for. When the entity is a data collection system, the API endpoints are called by the data collection cloud platform. Depending on the manufacturer, the API can passively wait to be utilised to offer the requested data, or can notify the data collection system of the availability of new data to be collected. The data loop back to the study participant is closed by one of the tasks of the mobile app of the data collection system: It utilizes another API, that of the data collection system, to get the integrated device data and visualise it alongside the rest of the secondary data it collects. While the usage of a 3rd-party API is very easy to support by the data collection system, the downside of the API approach is that many SW entities are involved (the two apps and the two cloud platforms) and the round trip of the data that travels from the device to the mobile phone, to two different cloud platforms back to the mobile phone, is very long. The device integration via the provided API is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Generic RWD collection mechanism where measurements utilize device API.

When a device manufacturer offers an SDK, then the data collection app receives the data from a local source, without involving the device cloud platform. The SDK can offer two different things. One option is direct access to the device. In this case the device is programmable and a part of the data collection system needs to be programmed in it. This will send the collected data to the data collection app of the mobile phone. Measuring via direct access to a programmable device via its SDK is depicted in Figure 3. The other option is indirect access to the device, via the device app running on the same mobile phone, as shown in

Figure 4. This is easier to implement, but demands both the device app and the data collection app to be running on the mobile phone.

Figure 3: Generic RWD collection mechanism where measurements utilize direct access to programmable device via its SDK.

Figure 4: Generic RWD collection mechanism where measurements utilize indirect access to device via its SDK on the device app.

A variant of the SDK access is when the devices being integrated are the actual sensors on the mobile phone. In this case, the SDK used is the phone's SDK, which is always well-known and documented. On Android devices a data collection service is programmed within the data collection app. On iPhone devices, the Apple Health Kit is used to access the data from Apple Health, the app that collects all health and wellness sensor data of the phone or other integrated devices. Similar solutions to Apple Health exist from all the big Android players (e.g., Samsung Health) but the Android manufacturer segmentation does not allow a data collection system to interface with one such app and get data from a significant portion of the possible study participants. Apart from Android manufacturer segmentation, another usability issue arises. For the mobile phone sensors to be used, the mobile phone must be used as a wearable, always in the pocket of the study participant, which is clearly not feasible for most people. Additionally, the location of measuring (i.e., the pocket) is of influence in the accelerometer-based estimation of a person's energy expenditure throughout the day. When using the mobile phone as a measurement device, this location of wearing is not

always known, and not always the same. Wrist-worn devices – especially when it is known whether the user is wearing it on the dominant or non-dominant hand, and therefore preferred.

Obviously, the easiest integration method is the API, but the most open to the needs of the data collection system is the SDK that allows direct access to a programmable device. Unfortunately, the device measurement method is not for the data collection system to select. Almost all device manufacturers offer API access to the collected data (the manufacturer maintains ownership of the data), while only a handful offer an SDK, and those that do usually represent more experimental and less commercial devices. Also, API usage is usually free, while SDK access is reserved for very large clients of the device manufacturers, or comes with a very high cost. Finally, device manufacturers can apply usage constraints in both modes of access, limiting the data attributes offered, the temporal granularity, the number of times data can be requested, or the volume of transferred data. All these aspects need to be taken into account when selecting the device to integrate.

3.1.2 Measuring physical activity in iHelp

The iHelp clinical partners have specified directly the use of a device for physical measurements, most of them agreeing that an activity tracker is much preferred over mobile phone sensing. They also indirectly specified the use of scales for weight collection. Only the physical measurement device (activity trackers or mobile phones) is reporting measurements automatically. The scales give the information to the study participant, to be entered manually into the system. It is thus the devices for physical activity measurements that are discussed in this section.

Currently, the iHelp physical measurement options in place are summarised in Table 3. Two well-known brands of activity trackers are directly covered: Fitbit and Garmin, both using API. Fitbit allows a certain number of API calls per day, and offers all information on the day up to that point, albeit without any information on when this data has been last updated. Garmin notifies whenever new information is available, and does provide some time series data, allowing intra-day information, though this is of no importance to iHelp, where no intra-day information is required. More activity trackers can be covered indirectly if devices are integrated with Apple Health. Integration with Apple Health utilised the Apple Health Kit SDK. Finally, the Android SDK is used in a module of the mobile app that captures the Android phone sensor signals.

Table 3: iHelp physical measurement options – integration methods and RWD collected.

Integrated devices	Integration method	RWD collected
Fitbit activity trackers	Fitbit API	Physical activity, exercise sessions, heart & sleep
Garmin activity trackers	Garmin API	Physical activity, exercise sessions, heart & sleep
iPhone sensors and devices integrated with Apple Health	Apple Health Kit (SDK)	Physical activity (with just the phone sensors)
Android sensors	Android SDK	Physical activity & exercise sessions

There is one difference between the Fitbit and Garmin measurements integration. Currently the integration with Garmin does not transfer any heart zone information requested by one of the clinical partners. A work-around this problem is currently sought, to get this information indirectly.

There is nothing to be done for the desired continuous heart monitoring without dedicated activity trackers. For sleep though there is the solution of start and end time reporting by the study participant, as discussed in Section 3.2.3.

Although automated measurements are secure in terms of data objectivity (a device measures and reports data without the intervention of the study participant) and quite low in terms of compliance burden onto the study participant, they do have some shortcomings:

- Devices do have an acquisition cost that has to be paid, and a study participant might need a few to fulfil the study protocol.
- Devices operate on battery; the study participant needs to make sure they are always charged, especially those meant for almost 24/7 usage.
- Not all devices can be integrated. It is easier for low volume and frequency measurements to be simply copied from the device's screen into the data collection system by the study participant.
- Some attributes cannot be measured; only the study participant can inform the system about certain aspects of their lives.

For these reasons, patient reports are still very important in studies. These reports are covered in Section 3.2.

3.2 Reporting from study participants

Study participants need to report on outcomes and their experiences, quantifying measures about them: the PROMs and PREMs. Traditionally the collection of the reports had been a manual process involving pen and paper, but now ePRO systems are facilitating this process in three important ways:

- Scheduled questionnaires can be addressed to study participants and the answers can be collected and processed much easier with the online ePRO tools.
- Spontaneous answers can be included with study participants reporting on outcomes and experiences at the moment they happen, without needing to collect them and report them at predefined times. This is very important for event-type outcomes like a symptom, affliction or discomfort. It is also important for manual measurement entry, like weight logging.
- Continuous editing for incremental data collection can be facilitated for attributes that need to be accumulated throughout the day (e.g., the daily water consumption is easier to report when the study participant just adds this information regularly in the day, or retrospectively for the previous one), or automated measurements that need some correction (e.g., the sleep start and end times). Both can be achieved using widgets, i.e., UI elements at the disposal of the study participant for continuous data entry.

Scheduled and ad hoc questionnaires, as well as widgets are discussed in the next sections.

3.2.1 Scheduled questionnaires

Scheduled questionnaires are addressed to study participants at regular intervals (daily, weekly, etc.). Although they can be custom, non-standard questionnaires, they usually are formal, well-established ones, used throughout the scientific community to collect a specific type of information. Often each question needs to be considered on its own, but it is not uncommon that an aggregated score is calculate over groups of questions.

The ePRO system facilitates scheduled questionnaires by presenting them to the study participant in a timely way (even in a clever one, if the participant is known to be otherwise pre-occupied at the exact moment). It utilises a variety of UI elements to facilitate data entry (e.g., multiple choice lists, tick-boxes, slide-bars, numerical entries, selection on images). It also offers advanced routing enabling or disabling groups of questions based on the study participant's status or previous answers.

3.2.2 Ad hoc questionnaires

Ad hoc questionnaires are at the disposal of the study participant for some spontaneous report. In many cases they are single-question, prompt-type ones (e.g., “please enter your weight in kilos,” or “Indicate the severity of your migraine.” All ad hoc questionnaires can be accessed using some “add event” UI element.

Ad hoc questionnaires should also be retrospective, allowing the study participant to change the time the report correspond to from the default “now” value to anything in the past. It is not easy to report a migraine the moment one suffers from it, but it is quite easy to remember about it in the next morning.

3.2.3 Widgets

Widgets are UI elements at the disposal of the study participant for continuous data monitoring, entry and correction. Attributes like liquid and food consumption can be collected more easily incrementally throughout the day instead of a one-off questionnaire at the end of it or the beginning of the next. Omissions and errors can be corrected retrospectively by revisiting previous days. Data can be visualised in natural ways, giving information back to the study participant, thus facilitating their compliance to the study protocol.

Also, widgets can be used to edit automatic measurements that are error-prone. E.g., the detected sleep start and end time, or the physical exercise type are automatically measured attributes that are usually error prone. The interested study participant can edit these attributes using the provided widgets.

3.3 iHelp secondary data inventory

Section 2 concluded with the iHelp clinical partner's wish-list for secondary data to be collected, while sections 3.1 and 3.2 gave an overview of the ways secondary data can be collected. In this section, the two are brought together, building the iHelp secondary data inventory and analysing it in terms of the needs from Healthentia, the RWD collection system employed in iHelp.

3.3.1 iHelp automated measurements

The iHelp automated measurements are shown in Table 4. For many attributes alternative measuring options and their shortcomings are given.

3.3.2 iHelp scheduled questionnaires

The iHelp scheduled questionnaires are detailed in Table 5. For every questionnaire an analysis of the implementation is also given.

Table 4: iHelp automated measurements.

Category	Attributes	Measuring options
Physical activity	Steps	Activity trackers via API (Garmin, Fitbit) Mobile phone via SDK (Android, Apple Health Kit)
	Floors Climbed	
	Energy burned	
	Time in different activity zones	Only with activity trackers
Exercise sessions	Start time	Activity trackers via API (Garmin, Fitbit) Mobile phone via SDK (Android, Apple Health Kit)
	Duration	
	Energy burned	
	Type	Multiple with API, only walk & run with Android SDK
Heart	Resting heart rate	Activity trackers via API (Garmin, Fitbit)
	Max heart rate	
	Time in different heart rate zones	Fitbit only, Garmin under investigation
Sleep	Start time	Activity trackers via API (Garmin, Fitbit)
	Duration	Mobile phone via SDK (Android, Apple Health Kit)
	Time in different sleep stages	Only with activity trackers

Table 5: iHelp scheduled formal questionnaires.

Questionnaire	Frequency	Scoring	Questions	Implementation
Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index [5]	Monthly	7 component scores summarised into a single global score	Two numerical and two time of day questions	Numerical and time input, grouped in one page
			20 questions to choose single out of four options	Single choice UI grouped in three pages
The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scales [9]	Start, middle and end of intervention	N/A	14 statements about feelings and thoughts, select one out of five options about their frequency in the past two weeks	Single choice UI grouped in 1 page
Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale [10]	Start, middle and end of intervention	Each statement is given 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree) points, negative statements 2, 5, 6, 8, 9 are reverse scored	10 statements about self-esteem, select one out of four options (strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree)	Single choice UI matrix with 4 columns, grouped in 1 page
Body Awareness Questionnaire [11]	Start, middle and end of intervention	Total scale score as a sum of the items, some being reverse-scored	18 statements about body awareness, scored on a 1-7 scale	Single choice UI matrix with 7 columns, grouped in 1 page
Subjective Happiness Scale [12]	Start, middle and end of intervention	Total score as a sum of the items, fourth being reverse-scored	Four statements about happiness, scored on a 1-7 scale	Single choice UI grouped in 1 page

Table 6: iHelp scheduled formal questionnaires (continued).

Questionnaire	Frequency	Scoring	Questions	Implementation
Locus of Control Questionnaire [13]	Start, middle and end of intervention	Total score as a sum of the items, some being reverse-scored	10 binary questions, each scoring 2 or 0	Single choice UI matrix with 2 columns, grouped in 1 page
Health Behaviour and Stages of Change Questionnaire [14]	Start, middle and end of intervention	N/A	5 groups of phrases related to different behaviours. 5 th group only applies to women	Single choice UI, one per page
Health literacy (HLS-EU_Q16) [16]	Start and end of intervention	Sum of the items (does not handle the missing items)	16 questions on how easy it is to follow different aspects of health (easy: 1, hard: 0, do not know: missing)	Single choice UI matrix with 3 columns, grouped in 1 page
Process of change questionnaire [17]	Quarterly	N/A	N/A	N/A
Smoking Habits	Biweekly	0-3 depending on answer	Single-question custom questionnaire: Have you smoked for the past two weeks? I have not smoked, or 1 cigarette per day, or 2-3 cigarettes per day, or 4 or more cigarettes per day	Single choice UI
Quality of Life (EQ-5D-5L) [18]	Start, middle and end of intervention	N/A	5 dimensions, 3 or 5 levels	Single choice UI matrix with 3 or 5 columns, grouped in 1 page
Quality of life for patients (EORTC QLQ-C30) [19]	Bi-monthly	N/A	28 questions with 5 levels	Single choice UI matrix with 4 columns, grouped in 4 pages
			2 questions with 7 levels	Single choice UI matrix with 7 columns, grouped in 1 page
Quality of life for pancreatic cancer patients (EORTC QLQ-PAN26) [20]	Bi-monthly	N/A	A continuation of the above questionnaire with 26 more questions with 4 levels	Single choice UI matrix with 4 columns, grouped in 4 pages
Edmonton Symptom Assessment System [8]	Daily	N/A	Intensity of nine common cancer patients' symptoms (pain, tiredness, nausea, depression, anxiety, drowsiness, appetite, well-being and shortness of breath)	0-10 horizontal slide-bars in single page
			Pain location	If pain, branch to body map
Activities of Daily Living [21]	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Please note that:

- The Food Frequency Questionnaire [6] is too long to be of practical use and too difficult to implement. The single partner requesting it accepted not to include it.
- The Food Diary with Rations [7] is not a questionnaire, but an almost free-text diary. The single partner requesting it accepted not to include it.
- The Edmonton Symptom Assessment System [5] has a final question about a custom patient reported symptom that cannot be automatically handled by the system. All symptoms of interest must be pre-defined. Other or the same symptoms can be collected also via the symptom ad hoc questionnaires shown in Table 8.
- The Health Literacy questionnaire (HLS-EU_Q16) [16] allows a third “do not know” answers that have no scoring info. The scoring system needs to be considered.
- There are different versions of the Process of change questionnaire [17] (alcohol, drug, reduced drinking, smoking) all of them either long or short. More information is needed on which to use.
- Information is needed on the official Activities of Daily Living questionnaire to be used.

Apart from the formal questionnaires listed in Table 5, there are some custom questionnaires addressed to the study participants. The final decisions and the design of these questionnaires are still pending, but the topics of interest encountered are listed in Table 7.

Table 7: Topics for iHelp custom scheduled questionnaires. Discussion, usage decision and design status.

Topic	Discussion	Usage	Design
Usage of social platforms	Ideally this could be measured by having the study participants connect their social media accounts to the data collection system. This is a process that most study participants will find difficult to follow. For this reason, the automated measurement can be replaced by a questionnaire that the interested iHelp clinical partners can design.	Decision pending	Pending
Opportunities for forming new health habits	Questionnaire with opportunities for forming new health habits	Start, middle and end of intervention period	Pending
Usage of mobile apps	In theory this could be collected automatically. Android collects this info and sends weekly reports to the users. But accessing these reports automatically by a SW system requires special permissions. There is no information about doing so in iOS devices. For these reasons the automated measurement can be replaced by a questionnaire that the interested iHelp clinical partners can design.	Decision pending	Pending
Diseases: diabetes, hypertension, pancreatitis, cirrhosis, hepatitis	Part of some initial questionnaire	Start of intervention	Pending
Family history of pancreatic cancer	Part of some initial questionnaire	Start of intervention	Pending

3.3.3 iHelp ad hoc questionnaires & reported measurements

The the ad hoc questionnaires and manually reported measurements used in iHelp are shown in Table 8. Their implementation with UI elements is also discussed. The symptoms are from [8].

Table 8: iHelp ad hoc questionnaires and manually reported measurements.

Attribute	Implementation
Height/weight	Numeric entry of manually measurement using non-integrated scales
Mood	Self-assessment using 5-level smileys
Pain symptom [8]	0-10 horizontal slide-bar, in not 0 also pain location body map
Tiredness, nausea, depression, anxiety, drowsiness, appetite, well-being and shortness of breath symptoms [8]	0-10 horizontal slide-bar
Supportive messaging	Free-form text input, capturing a message from a study participant towards all others. This message is pushed to the other study participants only after moderation from a HCP.
Overall health rating by participants [15]	Single question with six answers using the single choice UI
Pictorial questionnaire for self-assessment (Rockwood Frailty index) [22]	Single question with nine answers using the single choice UI

Please note that the frailty measure can be the specified ad hoc questionnaire, but it can also be the result of a composite measurement, having the study participants perform a sequence of scripted physical exercises, monitored with the mobile phone sensors.

3.3.4 iHelp widgets

Four widgets are currently envisioned for the iHelp secondary data collection: Sleep, liquids, food categories and e-diary. All these widgets can be enabled or disabled by the study administrators.

The role of the sleep widget is to view sleep duration and stages, as well as edit sleep duration. Its appearance on the main screen and its details once tapped are shown in Figure 5.

The role of the liquids' widget is to view and progressively or retrospectively add liquid consumption. Its appearance on the main screen and its details once tapped are shown in Figure 6. The widget has water consumption as the main attribute to be collected, but allows the study administrators to enable any of the coffee, tea, beverages and alcohol consumption attributes.

The food categories widget is similar to the liquids one, only now there are different food categories that are enabled or disabled by the study administrator. This widget is not designed yet.

The e-diary also displays reported information and allows access to the ad hoc questionnaires and manually reported measurements as shown in its daily and weekly details in Figure 7.

Finally, there are widgets that have only a data viewing and not a data collection role. These are the physical activity and the virtual coach widgets.

Figure 5: Sleep widget in main screen (left). Daily and weekly views (middle and right). The daily view facilitates edit.

Figure 6: Liquids' consumption widget in main screen (left) and daily details for data entry (right).

Figure 7: e-diary widget daily (left) and weekly (right) details. Data can be entered via the “Add report” button and the “+” UI elements.

4 Processing secondary data

Section 3 details the collection of raw secondary data, in the sense that it is data from measurements and reports as is, without any attempt to extract any higher-level meaning from it. This section is about processing raw secondary data, trying to establish higher-level information.

Currently the only higher-level information of interest to the clinical partners is the temporal evolution of the secondary data. For this habits and trends around them are established.

4.1 Habits

Behaviour is about habits and deviation from them. It is not so much about the current status. Hence any reasoning on behavioural data should regard the temporal evolution of secondary data. The temporal information for any quantity can be included by just using all d past samples of the quantity, but this leads to an unmanageable amount of input data. Another option is to use models of the past values: temporal evolution can be represented by assuming the normal distribution of the quantity, using its average and standard deviation.

Averages updated at every time step n with memory $a_n^{(d)}$ can approximate expectations of the k -th power of any RWD sequence x_n :

$$\overline{x_n^k}^{(d)} = a_n^{(d)} \cdot \overline{x_{n-1}^k}^{(d)} + (1 - a_n^{(d)}) x_n^k \quad (1)$$

where the memory is given by:

$$a_n^{(d)} = \begin{cases} 1 - 1/n & n < d \\ 1 - 1/d & n \geq d \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The parameter d can be considered as the length of the memory, i.e., the approximate days that influence the average.

Habits are established as the long-term averages of RWD. The memory in (2) can be short- or long-term depending on the choice of the memory length parameter d . E.g., a choice can be 7 for short-term averages (approximately, the last week is influencing short-term averages), and a value of 84 for long-term averages (approximately 12 weeks or 3 months influencing long-term averages).

Valid choices of d for getting habits and short-term averages are actually dictated by the duration of the studies.

4.2 Trends

There are deviations from some habit that can carry significant information about a study participant. The first order ($k = 1$) and second order ($k = 2$) averages yield the standard deviation estimates:

$$\sigma_n^{(d)} = \sqrt{\overline{x_n^2}^{(d)} - (\overline{x_n}^{(d)})^2} \quad (3)$$

The trend of some secondary data is defined as the variation in the short-term average from its long-term counterpart (the habit), normalized by the long-term standard deviation. The trend is then given by:

$$T_n = \frac{\overline{x_n}^{(d_{long})} - \overline{x_n}^{(d_{short})}}{\sigma_n^{(d_{long})}} \quad (4)$$

This definition of the trend makes it independent of the range of the secondary data in question. Small values around zero always designate a quantity that is currently at the level of the habit, not changing

significantly. Large positive trends indicate a deviation from a habit towards larger values, while large negative trends indicate deviating from a habit towards smaller values.

4.3 Temporal information

Temporal information about all collected RWD is added by using the short- and long-term averages, as well as their trends. While missing automated measurements are very unusual and an indication of some failure, missing values in the reports are normal. Nobody expects study participants to be entering normal body temperatures and lack of symptoms, thus in the above calculations one should consider missing reports in a day as indicating normality, and use the equivalent normal values in the updates.

5 Secondary data in the iHelp pipelines

Up to now, the description of the system facilitating secondary data capture has been abstract, focusing on the data collection options and not the specifics. This section dives into the specifics, addressing how Healthentia, a 3rd-party system is used “as a sensor” to gather secondary data and how this data finds its way into the iHelp platform and the HHR.

5.1 Integrating Healthentia with iHelp

In this section we first introduce the Healthentia platform, the measurement platform used in the iHelp project that is brought in as background and modified for the needs of the project by Innovation Sprint. Then, in Section 5.2 and Section 5.3, we discuss how Healthentia is integrated with the rest of the iHelp platform.

5.1.1 Healthentia e-clinical platform

The data collection is facilitated by Healthentia, an e-clinical platform. The platform provides secure, persistent data storage and role-based, GDPR-compliant access. It collects the data from the mobile applications of all study participants, facilitating smart services such as risk assessment, and providing both original and processed information to the mobile and portal applications for visualization. The high-level architecture of the platform is shown in Figure 8. This is a layered architecture, comprising of the API, data management, core functionalities, study management and services layers.

Figure 8: Healthentia high-level architecture.

The Healthentia API layer provides the means to connect Healthentia with the outside world. Data importing (IoT integration) and exporting (eCRF integration), as well as internal communication with the portal and mobile apps is facilitated through it.

The low-level operations on the data are hosted in the data management layer. The data handling functionalities are utilised by the API I/O endpoints. The smart data generation functionalities drive synthetic data generation.

The Healthentia core layer comprises of high-order functionalities on top of the data, like role-based control, participant management, participants' reports management and ML functionalities.

The study layer allows managing of the studies, the entities in which HCP, participants and their data are organized. They can be formal clinical studies, or informal ones managed by pharmaceutical companies, hospitals, or research centres.

Finally, the services layer implements the necessary functionalities of the web portal and the mobile application. These include dashboard services in both portal and mobile apps, e-diary for reporting by study participants and other services like treatment adherence, teleconsultation and smart services.

The Healthentia mobile application (Figure 9) enables data collection at the study participant end. Measurements are obtained from IoT devices, third-party mobile services or a proprietary sensing service. Study participants' reports are obtained via answering questionnaires that are either regularly pushed to the study participants' phones or are accessed on demand by the study participants themselves. Both the measured and reported data are displayed to the study participants, together with any insights offered by the smart services of the platform.

Figure 9: Healthentia mobile application.

The Healthentia portal application (Figure 10) targets the HCP. It provides an overview of the study participants of each clinical partner and details for each study participant. Both overview and details include analytics based on the collected data and the risk assessment insights. It also facilitates managing the studies, e.g., provides a questionnaire management system to determine the types of self-assessments and reports provided by the participants.

Figure 10: Healthentia portal application – viewing measurements and creating questionnaires.

5.1.2 Healthentia as a sensor

Other platforms employing Healthentia “as a sensor” utilize the eCRF integration API endpoints to get data. These endpoints facilitate individual or bulk data exporting towards authorized 3rd-party systems. In order for such systems to utilize the endpoints, they need to be authenticated. To this extend, Healthentia supports the “application” user role, a role intended for software systems and not humans. Such a system is authorized to access the data of certain studies and is given a pair of credentials. It then starts interacting with Healthentia by logging-in to obtain a token. Bearer authentication is then used in each call to authenticate the system and authorize access to certain RWD.

The data handling functionalities of the Healthentia data management layer is then employed under the hood to fetch the requested data.

The role-based control of the Healthentia core layer then handles authorization of data access. Other functionalities of this layer are also silently used to facilitate RWD collection, for managing participants and their reports.

Certainly, for RWD collection by different healthcare organizations, the functionalities to create and configure in-vivo studies of the Healthentia study layer are utilised at the setup phase, but also throughout the studies to monitor and manage them.

Finally, the functionalities of the Healthentia services layer allow the population of the mobile app dashboards and the collection of reports (e-diary). Both are important for the user experience of the study participants, to keep them interested in using the app by providing the sense that some information is fed back to them, allowing them to understand their conditions better.

5.2 Ingesting secondary data

Secondary data in iHelp are collected and processed with the help of a modified version of Healthentia capable of covering the needs of the clinical partners of iHelp. The Healthentia-powered iHelp secondary data system is positioned over the overall iHelp architecture in an adaptation from section 6.1 of D2.4 “Conceptual model and reference architecture I” shown in in Figure 11.

Figure 11: iHelp architecture and the role of Healthentia in it.

Secondary data collection spans two iHelp components, as detailed in D2.4 “Conceptual model and reference architecture I”:

- The mobile application handles reports from study participants. It is implemented by the Healthentia mobile application, suitable modified and branded for iHelp. It communicates with the secondary data pre-processor.

- The secondary data pre-processor handles automated measurement collection from 3rd-party devices and processes all raw secondary data into higher-level information. It is implemented by the Healthentia platform functioning as a sensor for iHelp. It communicates with the mobile application to receive reports and the Data Connectors component to offer the secondary data.

Identifiers of the study participants are registered in iHelp; as a result, both the iHelp platform and the secondary data collection system powered by Healthentia are aware of their users. The registration process is outlined in Section 5.2.1. Then, data ingestion can start, as outlined in Section 5.2.2.

5.2.1 Study participant registration

iHelp maintains the HHRs in a way so that it is possible to trace back all data to a particular study participant resource. The HHRs comprise of the primary and the secondary data. To do so, the study participants are registered with iHelp. The secondary data are gathered by a data collection system powered by Healthentia, thus Healthentia needs to know about the different studies involved and the participants in each one, i.e., the study participants are registered to studies of Healthentia.

There are five clinical partners in iHelp, each running their own study with different target populations and goals. Although there is a core of secondary data that is common across most studies, it is clear from Table 1 and Table 2 that there are many differences as well, especially in the scheduled and ad hoc questionnaires. To be able to support these changes, the secondary data collection system is based on five different Healthentia studies, one per clinical partner. This allows participants' segregation both for privacy and for management reasons. The process is as follows:

- A DPA is mutually agreed between each clinical partner and Innovation Sprint, where the clinical organization is designated as the study controller and Innovation Sprint the study processor.
- A Healthentia administrator (a user role of Healthentia and not used in iHelp at all) creates the organizations for the clinical partners that are not already using Healthentia, alongside with at least one organization administrator from each clinical partner.
- The organization administrator creates the iHelp study for their healthcare organization using the Healthentia portal application. If the organization administrator needs help with the subsequent steps, they invite some Healthentia administrator into their study.
- Any of the administrators involved can now proceed configuring the study. This is again done at the Healthentia portal application. The configuration involves creation of invitations for the study participants, creation of the questionnaires, selection of the widgets to be activated and creation of the investigators (the healthcare professionals monitoring the study). This latter role can be covered by the organization admin, or not be covered at all, since the use of Healthentia in iHelp stops at that point. Healthentia data of the studies are ingested into the iHelp big data platform, and any monitoring should be carried out with the tools therein.

For the study to begin, first the participants need to be registered to their respective studies in Healthentia. Healthentia does not need to know about the primary data and the complete HHR of the study participants. iHelp on the other hand needs to have the complete picture, so iHelp is naturally selected as the master in this process: new study participants are registered there, and this iHelp registration triggers the Healthentia registration. The registration is undertaken by an iHelp user with the HCP role and its details are beyond

the scope of this deliverable. The iHelp HCP and the Healthentia investigator can of course be the same person.

Healthentia study registration is done using an invitation code created during study configuration. This code is communicated to the iHelp study participant upon their registration, together with instructions on obtaining the branded version of the Healthentia mobile app for the particular study. The participants download the app and register themselves, adding their invitation code. This way the study participants also become Healthentia users with the study participant role. The email does not need to be real, but it does need to be unique. The registration is completed with every Healthentia study participant being assigned an ID.

After the registration is complete, the study participants are solely represented by their IDs. Any secondary ingestion will request individual data using an ID, or will receive bulk data for these IDs. For this reason, the IDs are made known to iHelp employing an API call that gets all registered participants for a study.

The registration process described uncovers the involvement of certain people via their use of SW components, in which case they have become users with different roles. During their involvement, they perform certain actions. The people, their user roles, their user actions and the SW components they use to perform them are listed in Table 9.

Table 9: The people involved in the iHelp studies, their user roles, their user actions and the SW components they use to perform them.

Person	User role	User actions	SW component
Healthentia administrator	Healthentia administrator	Creates new Healthentia organizations	Healthentia portal app
		Assists with study configuration	
HCP	iHelp HCP	iHelp study participants' registration, study monitoring	iHelp WebApp for HCP
	Healthentia organization administrator	Creates new study in their organization, and optionally configures it or invites Healthentia administrators to help out with the task	Healthentia portal app
	Healthentia investigator	Healthentia Study configuration, study participants invitation from iHelp to Healthentia, and optionally study monitoring	Healthentia portal app
Study participant	Healthentia study participant	User of the Healthentia mobile app to enter data and receive advice	Healthentia mobile app
	iHelp study participant	Passive role, having their account created at iHelp, always interacting with iHelp via the Healthentia mobile app	None

5.2.2 Data ingestion

After secondary data has been collected and pre-processed, they are periodically sent to the integrated iHelp platform so that they can be persistently stored and be accessible by the platform's analytical tools. For that, a data ingestion pipeline is periodically established that takes the responsibility of acquiring the data from Healthentia, applying all data processing related functionalities, and finally storing the data to the Big Data Platform of iHelp.

The data ingestion process involves two separate processes: the capture of the data, and the ingestion of the data. The data gateway implements the data capturing functionality. It provides different means for

data connectivity in order to access the data that might reside outside of the deployment of the integrated platform of iHelp. This is exactly the case with the secondary data, as they live inside the Healthentia platform that is considered an external source. Therefore, it makes use of REST clients to be able to connect and receive the related information periodically. The data provider, which in this case is the processor of the iHelp studies running with Healthentia, configures the gateway by invoking its interface and providing:

- The URI of the Healthentia exposed web services,
- The frequency that the data gateway needs to connect, and
- The definition of the schema of the provided data.

Then, a scheduler is being deployed that will periodically send REST requests to the provided URI, grab the data, transform them to the internal abstract entities and put them to a Kafka queue, along with data related meta-information (i.e., the definition of the schema).

After data has been initially captured by the data gateway, a specific data pipeline is established that consists of various analytical functions, whose purpose is to ensure the level of quality assurance, transform them to the common data model of HHR and finally persistently store them to the Big Data Platform of iHelp. These analytics functions related with the data ingestion might be domain/schema agnostic, and therefore they will rely on the definition of the schema of the secondary data, so that they can be in a position to properly deserialize and process them. They listen to the Kafka topic where the data gateway has put the captured data, and they apply their algorithms. Eventually, secondary data is received by the secondary *data mapper* that transforms them to HHR entities. As soon as they are transformed to HHR entities, the *data importer* receives them from a specific Kafka topic, establishes connection with the Big Data Platform and persistently stored them to the relational data model of the storage.

The deployment of the data pipeline related with the secondary data ingestion can be static or dynamic, thus can be automatically deployed each time such ingestion takes place. This happens in order not to waste valuable resources of the underlying infrastructure of the time that this data pipeline is inactive. However, this is the responsibility of the task T3.2 (“Primary Data Capture and Ingestion”) and it happens transparently for what concerns the activities described in this report. More information regarding the data ingestion can be also found in the corresponding deliverable D3.3 “Primary data capture and ingestion I”.

5.3 Mapping secondary data into HHR

The Secondary Mapper sub-component will enable the mapping of secondary data (e.g., from mobile, wearable and social-media platforms) into the common data model used by the iHelp platform (HHR). The component will provide necessary transformation functions that are required to map the secondary data from heterogeneous sources to the holistic health records that will be eventually stored in the iHelp platform – a conceptual schema of the HHR model is shown in Figure 12. The Secondary Data Mapper will be an integral part of the iHelp platform as it supports the enrichment of typical health records or EHRs individuals with the personalised secondary data (e.g., lifestyle, behavioural, social etc) coming from heterogeneous sources, including mobile and wearable devices.

Based on the microservice platform architecture model adopted in the iHelp project, the Secondary Data Mapper component will also be developed as a microservice. This microservice will expose API(s) to perform the conversions from a native data format or data model to a standard data modal and format, while applying any remapping and unit conversion required for different types of data fields or parameters. In this respect, the secondary data mapping functionality will comprise of the following (one or more) steps:

- Conversion to the standardised HHR format adopted in the iHelp platform
- Unit conversions to transform individual data parameters according to the predefined format
- Mapping specific concepts or data parameters to standardised HHR structure

In terms of implementation of the Secondary Data Mapper component, a schema library and data driven ingestion pipeline can be created to avoid heavily scenario specific code being developed.

Figure 12: Conceptual schema of the HHR model used in iHelp

The concept is to further breakdown the micro services approach to a chain of converters, mappers and meta data format tools that are built form a palette of common processes in each case being data driven on both the individual operation and the overall conversion process definition. The components of the Secondary Data Mapper microservice will be created as Docker containers drawn from a palette of images and controlled by environment variables and configuration files. In terms of functioning or operations, the Secondary Data Mapper will subscribe to the necessary Kafka message bus topics in the iHelp platform, do the needed mapping and then publish the mapped data back to the message bus for the data importer to receive and store in the iHelp big data platform.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable detailed secondary data collection, addressing the “what” and “how” to capture questions. The “what” originates from the clinical needs, resulting to raw data or data from processing. The “how” is dictated by technology. As a result, attributes of the secondary data can be automatically measured, or manually reported using scheduled or ad hoc questionnaires, or widgets. The “how” is further addressed by getting the secondary data from its source, the Healthentia-powered secondary data collection system, and ingesting it into iHelp. The process is concluded by mapping the secondary data into the iHelp HHR.

This deliverable is the early version of the secondary data collection system. Although it achieves its goal to address the “what” and “how” to capture questions, there are open issues to be addressed:

- The open issues in handling of some of the scheduled questionnaires and the design of the ad hoc questionnaires are listed in Section 3.3.2.
- The partition into automatically measured and reported secondary data can influence the clinical partners’ decision on what to include in their studies, resulting to changes in Table 1 and Table 2. The same can happen due to the cost of the involved activity trackers.
- Not all widgets are ready at the moment, as discussed in Section 3.3.4, and changes to the existing ones might be needed based on feedback.
- The processing of raw data described in Section 4 can change, as clinical partners become more used to the options they have at hand.
- Once the mechanics of the linkage between iHelp big data platform and Healthentia are finalised, the information in Section 5.2.1 might require an update.
- Finally, the secondary data mapping into HHR is a process that is just starting, as discussed in Section 5.3. This is work to be carried out in the next period.

The second version of this deliverable, D3.6 “Secondary data capture and interoperability II” to be delivered in M22 will address all these open issues.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
Dx.y	Deliverable of work-package x, numbered y
eCRF	Electronic Case Report Form (a software system used to collect data in a clinical study)
ePRO	Electronic Patient-Reported Outcome (a system to collect patient reports electronically)
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HCP	Healthcare Professional
HHR	Holistic Health Record (the iHelp version of health records)
ML	Machine Learning
Mx	Month x of the iHelp project, M1 being January 2021
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PREM	Patient-Reported Experience Measure
PROM	Patient-Reported Outcome Measure
RWD	Real-World Data
SDK	Software Development Kit
UI	User Interface